

FORMING AND PROMOTING A REGIONAL IMAGE, RETHINKING DESTINATION MARKETING AND BRANDING, AND MOVING BEYOND CONCEPTUAL CONFUSION.

Duschanov Alisher Sherzod ugli

Phd student at Urgench state university

named after Abu Rayhon Biruni

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Annotation. There is no consensus in the scientific literature on place promotion, place marketing and image, and place branding in practice as to the content of these three concepts and through what types of policies they can be implemented. Although a number of theoretical approaches and definitions have been proposed by scholars, both scholars and practitioners (consultants, civil servants, public and private stakeholders, and policymakers) often apply these concepts in an equal sense. This article argues that recent developments in theory and practice regarding territorial promotion, regional marketing, and regional branding provide an important opportunity to eliminate this conceptual confusion.

Keywords: image formation, destination branding, advertising of destinations, destination management.

Introduction

Policies aimed at shaping and promoting the image of regions, implementing marketing activities and branding are not new, however, their importance has increased significantly in recent decades [1,2]. In the case of cities, the basic hypothesis is that image formation and promotion, marketing and branding can support urban policies aimed at improving the destination for the benefit of residents, business entities and visitors. As more and more cities around the world implement these concepts into their operations, so does the confusion over their content and implications for urban politics. The diversity of approaches to destination promotion, regional marketing, and regional branding is directly related to the complex set of problems that cities have faced in recent decades, and it is these issues that have stimulated the formation of policies aimed at enhancing urban competitiveness [3,4]. We highlight the four main reasons that have led to the escalation of this process. First, described by Harvey as “a transformation in urban governance under late capitalism,” it is a process of transition from a managerial approach to an entrepreneurial approach in urban governance [5]. As a result of this “entrepreneurial turn,” terminology, concepts, tools, and mechanisms specific to the private sector have entered the public sector, and in almost all of them, competitiveness is seen as the primary goal.

Literature review

Promotion of territories

It is difficult to give a “clean” and precise definition to the concept of place promotion because most of the existing definitions overlap broadly with the concepts of regional marketing and regional branding, and usually use similar terminology, although often their content differs slightly. For example, Ward and Gold describe destination promotion as the conscious use of advertising and marketing in order to deliver selected images of specific geographic destinations or locations to the target market [6]. A deeper analysis of this definition shows that the term “marketing” as used herein does not refer to a broader conceptual interpretation of marketing, but to marketing communications as distinct from general advertising activities. Further, while terms specific to the concepts of branding (image) and marketing (target market) are used in this definition, they are used in different senses and in different ways. It is therefore not surprising that there is conceptual confusion. If an attempt is made to articulate the purpose of promoting a destination without using marketing or branding terminology, it can be defined as “drawing the attention of specific target audiences about the opportunities that the destination offers and hoping that demand will increase as a result.”

One of the most commonly used models in marketing communication is the AIDA model, which states that an increase in attention to specific offers can lead to the emergence of an interest, which in turn can form a desire and eventually lead to a particular action [7]. The point is that this model represents a unidirectional process, in which emphasis is placed squarely. The basic hypothesis of such a straightforward and hierarchical relationship between attention and action is precisely the main reason why public and private stakeholders initiate and support initiatives to promote the destination.

In the marketing mix, “promotion” is only one of the four “P’s” [8] or one of the seven “P’s” [9]. In this connection, it is important to note that most theoretical models proposed in the available scientific literature interpret territorial promotion as only one tool of regional marketing or regional branding [10]. In particular, **Ashworth and Voogd** identify promotional measures as one of the four key elements in their theoretical model of regional marketing [11], while **Kavaratzis** sees these promotional measures as a component of “secondary communication” in their theoretical model of regional branding [12]. Although there is a distinction between destination promotion and regional marketing in many theoretical models, the concept of “destination promotion” deserves special

attention because this concept encompasses almost entirely (if not entirely) the activities that most practitioners are doing, and even if they call it regional marketing or regional branding. This situation is clearly manifested in the practice of territorial promotion. The organizations responsible for these activities generally have little or no influence on the development processes that directly affect the formation of the proposals of the destination concerned. They often give priority to the launch of advocacy campaigns and the development and distribution of promotional materials that showcase the opportunities offered by the destination to (specific) target audiences in the target markets (certain). This process is determined by the missions, competencies of the organizations, and the different wishes of the many stakeholders involved in the process.

The use of visual identification (logo, slogan, color set, font, style) to define coordinated propaganda activities has become one of the main features of the promotion of the region, as well as advertising and almost indistinguishable propaganda campaigns. It is precisely such efforts that are expected by most stakeholders today. In our experience, this is more pronounced not only for public sector stakeholders but also for private stakeholders, especially when they are co-financing these organizations. The paradox is that the medium aimed at making an destination attractive and demonstrating its uniqueness often results in the same, similar (homogeneous) propaganda efforts.

Destination marketing

A number of definitions have been proposed in the scientific literature regarding what place marketing means or should be. Many of these definitions overlap in part with the concept of place promotion, but many of them also include other elements beyond that. For example, **Ashworth and Voogd** included “spatial-functional measures,” “organizational measures,” and even “financial measures” in regional marketing [11]. **Kotler and Haider** identified “infrastructure”, “essential services” and “attractions” as important components of regional marketing [13].

Although destination promotion is an important part of regional marketing, as can be seen from the above examples, the concept of zone marketing is much broader, encompassing many aspects and not just just promotional measures. Regional marketing is seen as one of the most important tools in the process of transitioning from a supply-oriented approach to a demand-oriented approach in urban development. For this reason, the consumer-oriented (customer) orientation is the central principle of regional marketing. For example, based on the American Marketing Association’s (2008) definition of marketing, Brown

defines regional marketing as follows, i.e., the coordinated use of marketing tools in the process of creating, delivering, communicating, and sharing urban offerings that have value for city customers and the urban community as a whole, supported by a single customer-centered philosophy [14].

Similarly, with a slight correction to the previous definition put forward by **Hospers** and **Lombarts**, it interprets regional marketing as follows, a long-term process or political tool consisting of interrelated but different activities aimed at retaining and attracting different target groups to a particular city [15].

Despite these definitions, in practice regional marketing is often used in the same sense as destination promotion. A good example of this is DMO (destination marketing organisation), a whole category of organizations operating in the tourism sector. DMOs often don't have the opportunity to radically change the directions they're in, but are mostly engaged in promoting them. In contrast, organizations engaged in foreign direct investment are usually called "investment promotion agencies" and this name is much more in line with their functions and powers. Since destination promotion is an integral and important part of regional marketing, organizations engaged in regional marketing will inevitably develop and apply promotional measures. This, in turn, serves to preserve conceptual confusion, since propaganda activities naturally attract more attention compared to other measures. As a result, as with destination promotion, stakeholders will continue to expect more prominent, limited activities than regional marketing. In practice, however, they may not even distinguish between these two concepts. This situation only adds to the terminological confusion, especially in cases where organizations involved in the promotion of the destination refer to their activities as regional marketing.

Destination brand

In 2005, Anholt had argued that the concept of place branding was being misinterpreted on a large scale [16]. The application of the concept of branding to the regions has since led to the emergence of numerous scientific works aimed at clarifying it for theoretical and practical purposes. In a recent study conducted among experts in the field of destination management, **de Noronha**, **Coca-Stefaniak**, and **Morrison** found that there are completely different interpretations of the concept of territorial branding [17]. As a result, conceptual confusion persists not only between different concepts, but also within each concept itself.

Some scholars prefer to see regional branding as one tool of regional marketing, while others, on the contrary, interpret regional marketing as a tool of

regional branding. This debate has a broader meaning than a simple debate between interrelated fields of science, implying that there are different schools of study. For example, a regional branding strategy based on a regional marketing approach may seek to develop different destination brands to enhance the competitive advantage of a destination among different target groups, i.e., it will focus on creating customized brands for different market segments. In contrast, a regional marketing approach based on regional branding promotes a strategy aimed at ensuring that all regional marketing efforts are aligned with a single brand. Although there are different views on whether regions “have a brand” or “a brand of themselves” [18], representatives of these two academic schools agree on the essence of a territorial brand. According to him, the brand of the destination is defined as “a network of associations formed in the minds of consumers, arising from the visual, verbal and behavioral expressions of the destination and its stakeholders. These associations differ within the network in terms of their impact and importance to the attitudes and behaviors of destination consumers.

Unfortunately, it still becomes necessary to state time and time again that the concept of “brand” is not the same as “logo” or “visual identity”. At the heart of regional branding are the concepts of identity and image. As Boisen points out, in regional branding, the identity of the destination is defined, distinguished, and coordinated, as a result of which the destination branding is enriched with positive associations. Ultimately, the main purpose of such practices is to improve the image of the destination.

Identity here does not mean all the existing aspects of an destination, but rather a coherent set of different forms of identity. On the one hand, territorial identity serves to distinguish an destination from other destinations, and on the other hand, it provides for the selection of material and intangible internal elements that correspond to the destination. This process is the process of realizing belonging to a destination, connecting oneself with it, and accepting it as unique.

When the identity of a destination is recognized, it becomes a promise and an expectation, that is, an image is formed. The image of a destination is how the destination is perceived. A strong image is formed when most people share the same associations, while a positive image is formed when these associations are evaluated as positive in a particular context. Ideally, there would be a high degree of correspondence between the identity of the destination and the image of the

destination. However, if the representatives of the target audience have not heard about the region at all, both identity and image have almost no power.

Therefore, attention (attention) is a prerequisite for regional branding. In other words, the aim of destination promotion is the starting point of regional branding. This suggests that it is counterproductive not to see destination promotion as a tool of regional branding. In the process of promoting the destination from the point of view of regional branding, the purpose of the promotion will change: it will no longer be limited to focusing only on the proposals of the destination, but also intending to turn this attention into awareness, which will have a positive impact on the image of the destination. The conscious and continuous shaping of the image is aimed at making a positive contribution to the overall reputation of the destination.

Referring to the corporate literature, the difference between destination imagery and destination image can be explained as follows: corporate image is the audience's immediately formed mental image of the organization. Corporate reputation, on the other hand, refers to the value given to a company's characteristics. Typically, corporate imagery is formed over time through consistent activity and effective communication, while a corporate image can be created relatively quickly through thoughtful communication programs.

Research methodology

This study aims to elaborate on conceptual approaches to regional image formation, regional marketing and regional branding, where qualitative research methods were used. In the course of the research, articles published in leading international scientific journals were selected, on which a systematic literature review was conducted. In particular, the theoretical foundations, methodological approaches and part of the conclusions of the selected scientific sources were studied using the methods of meaningful and comparative analysis. In the course of literature analysis, the content of the concepts of regional image, regional marketing and regional branding, their differences and dependencies, as well as the role of these concepts in regional development policies were clarified. Based on the results obtained, the existing scientific approaches were generalized and important theoretical conclusions were formed. This methodological approach serves to systematize the scientific views on the research topic, as well as to enrich the theoretical base on regional image and branding.

Results and discussion

The common essence of the concepts of place promotion, place marketing and place branding is considered to be close to each other (Figure 1). While they

are interrelated and adjacent to each other, they are three distinct concepts that use different means to achieve their goals. This reframing helps clarify the confusion around these concepts and serves as a guide for policy formulation, institutionalization, and implementation. This classification introduces conceptual clarity regarding the structure of relationships between concepts, as well as their functions, powers and expected outcomes. Since tasks, competencies, goals, and outcomes are all different, it makes sense to conclude that organizational aspects must also be different in order to ensure effectiveness and effectiveness. Therefore, this distinction is also useful in determining how to use and implement these concepts in policies aimed at enhancing the attractiveness, image and image of a destination.

	Destination promotion	Destination marketing	Destination branding
Approach	Based on the proposal; From the sender to the receiver is directed;	On-demand; From the outside to the inside (needs);	identity-based; From the inside to the outside (relevance);
Objectives Mandate Budget	Delivery of proposals; Coordinated outreach; Target audiences;	Supply and demand management; Product-market combinations; Target market segments;	Governance of Governance; Image coordination; concepts that connect with destination in the minds of the audience;
Results:	Attention	Choice	Reputation
Main Destination:	Cognitive* (knowledge)	Conative* (behavior)	Affective* (attitudes)

Note (*) It is important to note that all three concepts relate to the three domains (cognitive, cognitive, and affective) to some extent. The differentiation presented here is given in order to distinguish them from each and to emphasize the leading field to which the main results of each belong.

Figure 1. The differences between destination promotion, destination marketing, and destination branding.

It can be seen that the task of destination marketing is broader than the task of promoting the destination, as it involves not only indirect influence on the development of the destination through promotional measures, but also direct influence through the formation of product market combinations of the destination that are important for the target groups in strategically selected market segments [14].

Ideally, the organizational unit involved in destination marketing should have a strong mandate to provide direction to other organizations and stakeholders, including the ability to influence the development of the destination itself. Unlike zone marketing, the main function of destination branding is to drive reputation. Coordinating the image of the destination in a holistic way requires a stronger mandate and a broader base of influence over destination marketing [19].

In fact, destination branding should be able to influence all of the factors that significantly affect how the destination is perceived. The process is much more complicated for territories than corporations, and the main reason for this is the presence of a political dimension. As Terlow points out, the definition of territorial identity is often the subject of debate between public and private stakeholders and is therefore often the subject of political debate.

Similarly, Lucarelli describes destination branding as "a political process that manifests itself as political intervention, a process that has the potential to shape new spaces." To achieve this, destination branding should be an integral part of overall city policies and strategies, i.e., the pillar of city governance. To do this, compared to destination marketing, zone branding requires a broader political and governance support base, collaboration with more (and diverse) stakeholders on a wider range of topics, and a higher level of expertise within the organization.

In Figure 2, we illustrate the relationship between destination promotion, destination marketing, destination branding, and destination development, with the strands representing the desired direction of impact. Here, the concept of "destination development" is used as a generalizing term, which includes the proposals of the destination and other aspects of urban governance that are directly aimed at creating or improving the destination itself.

Our reinterpretation of destination promotion, destination marketing, and zone branding (Figure 1) can also be applied to clarify policies that target different market segments. Figure 3 illustrates the relationship between these three concepts and the three dominant market segments (business entities, population, and visitors). This image also shows that the promotion of the destination as a means is mainly focused on increasing attention to what the destination has to offer at this time. Therefore, in the absence of a broader, longer-term strategy, destination promotion tends to be short-term, emphasizing exactly which proposals should be brought into the spotlight at that moment. In contrast, destination marketing is mainly focused on supply and demand management,

which requires a long-term strategy and approach, as well as a high level of market segmentation and product/service development [14].

Figure 2. Destination marketing, destination development, destination advocacy and destination branding.

This means that destination marketing must simultaneously focus on both the present and the future, adapt the destination’s offerings to take into account changing needs and trends. In the case of destination branding, a high degree of selectivity and long-term consistency are required in the development and promotion of the destination.

The main hypothesis put forward in this article is that there is a sequential (gradual) relationship between the three concepts in terms of institutionalization and implementation. In contrast to the corporate context, where marketing can sometimes take precedence over branding, we believe that in the case of territories, zone branding should take precedence over destination marketing and destination marketing over destination promotion to ensure efficiency and effectiveness (Figure 2).

Where destination marketing can focus on specific market segments, destination branding by its very nature requires influencing the integrity of the destination. This represents the complexity of management, as well as the

widening of the political, managerial and managerial support base as we move from left to right in Figure 1.

The interdependence of the three concepts retains conceptual confusion, but ignoring their differences can lead to imbalances between goals, means, and outcomes. In practice, the official function of an organization involved in destination promotion, destination marketing, and destination branding might be defined as “destination image enhancement” (i.e. reputation- destination branding). But there is a high probability that the mandate of the same organization will be limited only to coordinating propaganda activities (promotion of attention). Complicating matters further, such an organization is often evaluated on the basis of indicators such as increase in the number of visitors, longer stay, increased expense and increased revenue (the choice is destination marketing). Such imbalances between tasks, powers, and evaluation criteria not only reduce the effectiveness and effectiveness of an organization, but can also undermine the stability of the organizational structure, jeopardizing the legitimacy and even the *raison d'être* of the organization. In order to avoid such hindrance imbalances, appropriate powers and tasks should be given to the organizations responsible for specific purposes, and their activities and results should be evaluated accordingly. This is especially important when selecting key performance indicators (KPIs) and setting organizational goals. In practice, such imbalances are common. When it comes to promoting the destination, city governments often delegate tasks such as promoting tourism, attracting investment, promoting exports, and attracting talent to individual organizations. These organizations can even operate at different territorial-administrative levels (e.g., a local destination marketing organization for tourism and a regional agency for investment). However, it is likely that imbalances will persist even when these tasks are delegated to a single, integrated authority. As noted above, authorities are often cautious about giving authority to organizations engaged in destination marketing to have a significant impact on the destination's real development. As a result, these organizations are held accountable for outcomes that they cannot adequately influence. In addition, authorities often fail to adequately understand the need for the organization that manages the destination brand to be in a position where it can provide consistently brand-appropriate destination marketing, destination promotion, and destination development. In recent years, some cities have begun to look for new forms of destination promotion, destination marketing and/or destination branding in order to eliminate such imbalances. Uzbekistan, for example, recently set up an internal organization

responsible for destination branding. Through this, it is envisaged to allow destination branding to have a greater impact on city policies, while maintaining an external marketing organization to adapt to the needs of target groups [20]. The main tourism destinations of Uzbekistan, on the other hand, chose a different organizational model and formed an external team to manage the region's brand. At the same time, it is aimed to separate the tasks, powers and responsibilities related to zone branding from the marketing of the destination, but no new integrated organization has been created. As a result, Visit Uzbekistan remains the destination marketing organization responsible for visitor-oriented product market combinations. In this process, the structure that manages the brand of the destination provides guidance and is evaluated on the basis of the degree of success in performing this particular task. As noted in the introduction, most empirical research on the applicability of these concepts to territories consists of case studies. The differentiations proposed in this paper allow for a more systematic analysis of the tasks and competencies of the responsible organizations, how they align with the activities and projects they are undertaking, how these activities are assessed, and how they relate to the expectations and needs of different stakeholders, rather than directly adopting the terminology of the destination being analyzed for the researcher. Similarly, empirical research on effectiveness measurement and organizational effectiveness can benefit from conceptual clarity, as it raises other questions about what should be evaluated and what should be measured. Finally, by clarifying the content of these concepts, this article can contribute to a long-overdue debate about the extent to which territories should be governed by the requirements of these concepts and tools.

Conclusion

The conceptual confusion surrounding destination promotion, destination marketing, and destination branding stems from the complexity of the diverse and ever-changing practices of cities aimed at increasing their competitiveness. In this paper, we have shown that beneath this diversity there are commonalities both in theoretical academic reasoning and in practical application. Recent academic debates about the differences between the three concepts and the study of their impact on modern urban governance have provided us with the basic elements needed to create a more coherent conceptual framework (framework). This conceptual framework helps differentiate destination promotion, destination marketing, and zone branding from each other; It provides an opportunity for academics to conduct analyses in a structured manner, to analyse

and compare results, and for practitioners to develop more consistent policies, form better organizations, and avoid imbalances that hinder the process of clearly defining the missions, powers and goals of these organizations. In the process of developing a conceptual framework based on the differences between the three concepts, we came to the following conclusions: the promotion of the destination is limited to increasing the focus on the current proposals of the territories. Destination marketing, on the other hand, focuses primarily on fine-tuning the destination to drive supply and demand, a process that includes promotional measures as well as other measures aimed at improving product-market combinations. Therefore, destination marketing benefits from an integrated approach and should not be conducted in isolation from the real development of the destination. In addition, we found that destination branding is the most inclusive of the three concepts, and that it is the most required of organizational capacity. For destination branding to be a meaningful tool, it cannot exist as a separate political orientation or external organizational structure, but rather it requires deeper integration even in relation to destination marketing. It is important to note that conceptual clarity is not just an academic exercise and has a much broader significance than simple semantic discussion. Conceptual clarity allows researchers to classify, while practitioners allow for more consistent and rational coordination of tasks, competencies, target indicators, and end goals in destinations that correspond to each of these three concepts.

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